

BAJRAMATHA (GYARASPUR) : A SURYA TEMPLE

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Vidisa the ancient mercantile city of the time of rulers like Asoka, Agnimitra and Chandragupta-II was a focal point of various cultures from the Mauryan times to about the Mughal times as is evident from the remains of these periods located in and around the town and throughout the district.

A good collection of images may be seen in Gwalior Museum (Gujarimahal) of which the most outstanding figure is that of a Salabhanjika from Gyaraspur of international fame.

Out of all the outstanding monuments and remains of the Vidisa district, only Bajramatha of Gyaraspur has been selected for discussion in this article. It is proposed to decide whether it is a Jaina temple, a group of Brahmanical temples or purely a Surya temple.

Gyaraspur, flourishing temple-city of the days of the Pratiharas and the Paramaras, is presently a village located at a distance of about thirty five km. from Vidisa, on the Vidisa-Sagar road. A number of outstanding monuments like Maladevi temple on the south is situated on the top of the hill. Hindolatorana inside the village, Athakhambha in the west were built during the period, Bajramatha or Bajramatha on the south-west ranging from eighth to tenth century A.D. Apart from these, there are certain ruined monuments, such as Buddhist stupas and images and remains of two temples to the north of the village, Manasarovara tank and the ruins of a gadhi or fort are worth mentioning¹. This village containing the monuments and remains of Brahmanical, Buddhist and Jaina faiths may be termed as the Triveni of confluence of all the three religious sects.

Bajramatha, a Brahmanical temple, on the

south-western skirts of the village, is an example of unique and rare class of temple, containing three shrines side by side in a row. At present, images of Jaina Tirthankaras are enshrined in the Garbhagrihas of all the three shrines.

According to Cunningham "The Bajramatha is a fine example of a very rare class of temple containing three separate cells in a row. The central cell is 7 ft. 4 inches long and each of the side cells are a foot less. All the three cells are now occupied by Jaina figures; but it is quite certain that it was originally a Brahmanical temple, as all the outside niches are filled with Brahmanical figures. The figures over the doorways of the cells are also Brahmanical, the central cell having Surya in his seven horses chariot with Brahma and Vishnu to the left and right. I therefore, conclude, that the temple, having been desecrated by the Muhammadens, was deserted for a long time and then at a later date was appropriated by the Jains. The naked statues which are now seen inside the temple were probably brought from the Jaina temple of Maladevi on the top of the hill."²

Dr. Patil has expressed his view regarding this temple in the following manner:³

"It is the example of a rare class of temple containing three shrines in a row. All the three shrines are now occupied by Jaina idols but the sculptures on the door-frames of the shrines and the niches on the basements of the temple clearly show that it was originally a Brahmanical temple in which three shrines dedicated to the principal gods of the Hindu Trinity are combined. The central shrine is sacred to Surya who is often substituted for Brahma, the southern to Visnu and the northern to Siva."

Right door Jamb of the Surya shrine of the temple Bajaramatha.

Lintel of the Surya shrine of the temple Bajaramatha.

According to Dr. Nagarch⁴ "Bajaramatha belongs to a rare class of temples. It is a triple shrined temple having a common Mandapa in front. The central shrine is dedicated to Surya while the southern and the northern shrines are sacred to Siva and Visnu respectively." He has further expressed : "Dvadasadityas i.e., twelve of Suns are represented standing on the fourth sakha of the doorway of the central shrine, lintel and the niches near the ceiling."

"Ekadasa Rudras are represented standing on the fourth sakha of the doorway of the southern shrine and in the niches above the door-lintel and near the ceiling."

"Dasavataras (ten incarnations) of Visnu are depicted on the third sakha of the doorway of the northern shrine, lintel and the three niches of the doorway."⁵

It is, thus, quite evident from the above statements of A. Cunnigham, D.R. Patil and Nagarch that they have accepted it as a Hindu or Brahmanical temple alongwith the fact that the temple contains three shrines in a row. They have also accepted the installation of Jaina Tirthankara images inside the Garbhagrihas. However, none of them has cared to throw light on the issue whether this temple is a Surya temple or not.

It is a triple shrine temple with a sixteen pillared common mandapa in front of which 5 pillars and 4 pilasters are presently in existence and a solitary sikhara surmounting the central shrine which is actually the main shrine dedicated to Surya. The temple facing east stands on a low platform (Jagati) approached by a flight of four steps. The Jagati measures 14.87 m x 15.14 m in length and breadth and is about 1 m in height. Thus, it is almost a square.

The temple stands on the centre of this Jagati and measures 9.30 m east-west and 10m north-south on plan. The temple consists of triple shrines in an alignment alongwith a common mandapa in front. The central shrine is dedicated to Surya while the southern shrine is sacred to Siva and the northern one to Vishnu. Amongst these three shrines, the

central one dedicated to Surya is the main shrine whereas the shrines to the South and North dedicated to Siva and Visnu respectively are subsidiary shrines, which is evident from the fact that they are one foot less in size than the central cell.

The central shrine enshrines the image of Risabhanatha along with his emblem, the bull on the pedestal. The image is seated in Padmasana. The Parikara is decorated with trichhatra, Dundubhika, and flying Vidyadharas etc. This image is datable to c. 12 cent. A.D. The Garbhagriha is plain inside and square on plan, measuring 7 ft. 4 inches each side. Its doorway is Trisakha-Dvara which is exquisitely carved in three branches (Photograph 2). The innermost branch contains the image of standing Ganga on the left and Yamuna on the right. Above the river goddesses on this branch is the decoration of a diamond and floral design. On the Naga-vallari in twisted form and the Padma-Vallari in the curvatures of the same are depicted with the figures of dancing Ganas and Gandharvas playing on musical instruments. In the central branch, eight Surya figures have been shown as standing in Samabhanga mudra, on above the other, on the both the sakhas of the doorway (Photograph 3).

One image of Surya is shown seated in a chariot driven by seven horses on the lintel (Lalata-Bimba) and three figures standing in Samabhanga mudra in three niches, i.e. one each niche above the lintel. (Photograph 4). The image of Surya on the Lalata-Bimba has a halo ornamented with lotus around the head which is damaged. The portion of his leg below the thighs and his hands below the elbow and the head of seven horses of his chariot are also broken off. He wears Vaikakshaka, hara, Kavacha and Keyuras.

The heads of all the three images in the niches are damaged. Each of them is two-armed holding full-blown lotus in each of his hands. Each of them is flanked on either side by standing Pingala and Dandi. Each image of Surya shows Aruna in between his legs and is flanked on either side by Usha and Pratyusa shooting arrows of light. Chhaya and

Door Jamb of Surya Shrine of Bajaramatha.

General view of the temple Bajaramatha.

Sanjna, the consorts of Surya, are holding a lotus with stalk in one of their hands.

The above details clearly speak that this main shrine was originally dedicated to Surya and the twelve Surya images on the doorway lintel and niches near the ceiling represent the Dvadasadityas as has been established by Nagarch⁶, but in the absence of the Ayudhas, due to all broken hands, nothing can be surely established.

On the right side of the main shrine of Surya is the subsidiary shrine dedicated to Siva in the southern direction. The Garbhagriha inside is plain and square on plan measuring 6 ft. 4 inches square. Inside the Garbhagriha is installed an image of Rishabhanatha, the first Jaina Tirthankara seated in Dhyanamudra on a simhasana.

The doorway of this shrine is also elaborately carved in the pattern of a Surya shrine. The middle sakha of the jamb is decorated with four chaturbhujia Siva figures on either side. Thus, total of Siva images on both the door-jamb is eight in number. Three Siva images have been installed in the three niches above the doorway lintel, i.e., one in each niche. Each of the three images is flanked on either side by a standing Chamaradharini.

These female attendants are partially damaged. There is an image of Siva on the Lalatabimba which is almost lost. This image is flanked on either side by a Vidhyadhara Yugala. Thus, total images of Siva on the doorjamb, lintel and niches, above the lintel are twelve⁷.

The exteriormost branch of the doorway is adorned with the figures of the Dandadhara Siva. The decoration of this doorway is almost similar to the doorway of Surya consisting of the patterns of Padmavallari, floral and diamond designs.

On the north of the Surya shrine, is the shrine of Visnu, but inside the Garbhagriha images of Tirthankaras are enshrined at present. Amongst these Tirthankaras are, Neminatha with his Yaksa Bhrikuti and Yakshini Gandhari. On the right of this is the image of Rishabhanatha and on the left are the images

of Parsvanatha and Suparsvanatha in Khadgasana mudra. These images may be assigned to c. 11th Cent. A.D. on stylistic grounds.

The doorway of the shrine is a Tri-sakha-Dvara. On the left jamb is Ganga and on the right jamb is Yamuna. The central branch is decorated with the figure of a female attendant on either side, above which are four figures of Visnu on either side, standing in Tribhanga mudra. These figures of Vishnu are adorned with a canopy of five serpent-hoods. They may be termed as Vaikuntha, Narayana or Adimurti. On the Lalatabimba is the figure of Garudasina Vishnu which is almost lost. Above the lintel, there are three niches occupied by images of standing Chaturbhujia Visnu in Samabhanga mudra flanked on either side by a standing female attendant, holding a lotus with stalk in one of her hands. In this way, there are altogether twelve images of Visnu and not ten (Dasavatars) as stated by Nagarch⁸. No Avatara forms have been delineated on this doorway.

The central shrine is surmounted by a tall pancharatha sikhara decorated with a mesh of Chaitya-Gavakshas. Its Karnarathas are ornamented with Bhumi-amalakas. The shrines on its southern and northern sides have the pyramidal sikharas which are ultimately joined with the central sikhara.

The Jangha (wall portion) of the temple is decorated with two bands of sculptures but the back wall of the central shrine contains only one band of figures which is continued throughout.

The position of Astadikpalas depicted on the Jangha clearly speaks that the temple-complex is one and one only. Amongst the images are - (1) four-armed Indra standing in tribhanga mudra and carrying vajra (2) two-armed Agni standing in tribhanga mudra and extending abhayamudra with flames issuing out from his head (Photograph 5), (3) four-armed Yama with a ferocious look and bulging eyes and protruding teeth, his mount buffalo is depicted to his left, (4) Four-armed Nirriti standing in tribhanga mudra is shown nude (5) Varuna standing; his hands, heads and right leg are broken

Agni-on the back Jangha of the temple, Bajaramatha.

(6) Vayu standing, his head and legs are broken. A mutilated bull has been depicted as his mount, which seems to be a mistake for deer (7) four-armed Kubera standing in tribhanga mudra, his head and arms are broken and (8) two-armed Isana carrying trisula in one of his hands. His mount bull is depicted to his left.

The temple on the jangha portion delineates the images of Matrikas. They are (1) four-armed Varahi dancing on Garuda. All of her arms are broken. She is attired with Karandamukuta and embellished with Kundalas, Kanthahara, Keyuras, ekavali her undergarment is fastened by a belt with loops and tassels. She has placed her right foot on Garuda. This is a rare piece of sculpture (2) Dancing Chamunda is almost mutilated, but her ribs and drooping breasts are clearly visible (3) four-armed dancing Indrani, whose arms are partly broken, her Vahana, the elephant, is shown seated behind her. Her Mukuta, ornaments and garments are similar to those of Chamunda (4) four-armed dancing varahi holding fish and ghata, her other two hands are mutilated. She is embellished with a torgue, ekavali, Keyuras, Valayas, nupuras and garment like those of other Matrikas (5) four-armed dancing Kaumari is badly damaged. She holds sakti in her upper left hand which is in traces. She is adorned with ekavali, keyuras and long mala. Halo is provided behind her head; her Vahana, the peacock, is standing beside her left side (6) Dancing Brahmi, attired with Karandamukuta and embellished with a torgue, Kundalas, ekavali, Keyuras, valayas and nupuras along with an undergarment fastened by a belt with loops and tassels.

Other images depicted on the bhadras and the Jangha, are Vaisnava, Saiva, Vighraha, murtis and the Surya images occupying important places. There are Nayikas and Surasundaris alternating with the gods and goddesses.

Among the Saivite images are (1) Nataraja in a small niche carrying Gajatunda, puspa and showing pataka-mudra (2) Another image of Nataraja is in a niche, holding sarpa in one hand above the image of

Indrani. His Vahana, the Nandi, is shown standing to his right. He is crowned with Jatamukuta, and embellished with a torgue, Yajnopavita and Vyagracharma. (3) Ashtabhuj Nataraja is in a niche of the lower band. His figure is almost broken. To his left is Nandi while on his right is depicted a male drummer. He is crowned by an Udgama (4) Tripurantaka Siva, destroying the cities of the Asura Tripura. He is standing in Pratyaldha posture and shooting an arrow on the bow. He is adorned with Jatamukuta and is attended by a female attendant on either side (5) Harihara standing in Samabhanga mudra, his right half is of Siva, while the left half is that of Visnu. The Mukuta adorning the deity is Jatamukuta on the right half while the left half has Kiritamukuta. There is a halo behind his head (6) four-armed Ardhanarisvara is standing in samabhanga mudra. All his four arms are broken. Being a combination of Siva and Sakti, his right half is that of Siva, while the left half is that of Parvati. A halo is provided behind his head. The mounts bull and lion are seated to his right and left respectively (7) four-armed Ganesa stands in tribhanga mudra.

The Vaisnava images adorning the Jangha of the temple are as follows :-

- (1) Four-armed Nrisimha in a niche above the image of Surya. He is ripping open the belly of Hiranyakasyapa with his two hands.
- (2) Four-armed standing Balarama showing Varada mudra and holding hala, Gada and Kamandalu. He is installed in a niche on the top. Above his head is a serpent-canopy.
- (3) Four-armed Varaha in an upper niche is uplifting the earth goddess.
- (4) Four-armed Yoganarayana (Visnu) is seated in Yogasana in a niche above the niche of Nataraja. His two lower arms are in Dhyana Mudra, and his upper arms hold Gada and Chakra.

The images of Surya have occupied important places on the Jangha portion of the temple. These are three in number :-

- (1) The first image is enshrined on the southern wall of the Jangha in a niche on the Bhadraratha. It stands in samabhanga mudra in an udichyavesa, attended by Pingala and Dandi, on his right and left respectively. Pingala carries pen and inkpot while Dandi takes a long staff. The image is attired with Kiritamukuta and is embellished with Vaikakshaka, Keyuras, Kavacha, Yajnopavita and his undergarment is fastened by a belt with loops and tassels. There is a halo behind his head and his arms are mutilated.
- (2) An image of four-armed Surya stands in Samabhanga mudra in a niche of the lower band of the Jangha on the back wall. He holds Sanalapadma in his two upper hands, the lower right hand is broken, while the lower left is placed on the head of Dandi, who is standing on his left holding a staff. On the right is standing Pingala holding an inkpot in his right hand.
- (3) The third Surya image occupies a niche of the Bhadra on the northern Jangha of the temple. This two-armed image stands in samabhanga mudra crowned by a pediment of chaitya - arches. His head is completely broken; but the halo behind his head is still visible. It holds sanalapadma in one of its hands, while his other hand is broken. It is adorned with Vaikakshaka, a long garland, Ratna Yajnopavita, armour and long boots and its undergarment is similar to those of other Surya images. On its right is standing Pingala while on left is Dandi.

The position of these Surya images on the south and north Bhadra niches and on the west in a niche of the lower band of the Jangha clearly speaks the major importance of the deity. Apart from the above-mentioned images, most noteworthy are the Surasundaris and Nayikas of which Alasakanya and Sringarika are outstanding from the point of view of their modelling.

CONCLUSION :

- (1) In view of the details mentioned above, it is an established fact that Bajaramatha (Vajramatha) was originally a Surya Temple. Since every temple is dedicated to one god only, this temple is also dedicated to Surya occupying the central shrine along with the subsidiary shrines of Siva on the south as well as Visnu on the north, on its either side. Moreover, the shrines of Siva and Vishnu are one foot lesser in dimensions in comparison to the Surya shrine which ultimately proves them to be the subsidiary shrines. All the three shrines can not be treated as independent shrines and also not as a Tri-ayatana temple⁹ as suggested by Nagarch. In the seminar at Vidisa held on 22nd Oct. 1989, in his discussion on my present paper his theory was not accepted. Out of the three shrines, the Surya shrine is the main shrine which is surmounted by a pancharatha sikhara. Apart from the twelve images of Surya delineated on the doorway as Dvadasadityas the images of this deity occupy the southern and northern Bhadra Ratha niches along with an image of Surya enshrined in a niche of the lower band of the Jangha on the west. Firstly, being the central shrine surmounting by the main sikhara and secondly placing of the images on important positions is the sufficient ground to prove that the temple is dedicated to Surya only, and thus, it is undoubtedly a Surya temple. Thirdly, the central deity on the lalatabimba represents the Surya which is a sure indication of the fact.
- (2) The theory of Nagarch¹⁰ regarding the Dvadasadityas on the basis of the twelve Surya images on the doorway of the Surya shrine stands to some extent, but as far as Ekadasarudras and Dasavataras are concerned in view of the images depicted on the doorways of the Siva and Visnu shrines, his derivations do not seem to be convincing, because the

images on both these doorways are twelve and not eleven and ten respectively.

- (3) The representation of Astadikpalas on the northern, southern and western Jangha clearly bring out their importance that the temple is a single complex.
- (4) The images of dancing Matrikas, different forms of Siva as Nataraja, Tripurantaka, Harihara and Ardhanarisvara and Avataras of Vishnu, like Nrisimha and Varaha, reflects the unity in diversity and spirit of tolerance amongst the different sects i.e., Soura, Saiva and Vaishnava, existing during the Pratihara age.
- (5) The style of sculptures, no doubt, maintains elegance and balance, and spiritual ecstasy, but it could not achieve the performance of Gupta period. The sculptures are more ornamental in comparison to the Gupta sculptures, but less ornamental than the sculptures of the Paramara, Chandela and Kachchhapaghata sculptures whose ornamentation can be termed as over-ornamentation.

Thus, the style of the sculptures has an elegant simplicity and represents sophistication as well as sensitive figure-work; but the sculptures of Telika-mandir, Gwalior fort and Maladevi temple here are far expressive and more elegantly worked out, than the sculptures of this Sun temple. This temple is assignable roughly to later half of the ninth Cen. A.D. on stylistic grounds.

- (6) Although it is evidently proved to be a Surya temple, we can not overlook the idea of the architect to give it a form of Hari-Hararka since all the three deities i.e., Surya-Siva and Visnu are present in the different shrines standing in a row.

Last but not the least is the fact that this temple is a rare and unique example on its plan containing three shrines in a row which is totally absent in the whole of the State of Madhya Pradesh.

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5. Ibid, p. 147.
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9. A seminar was organised at Vidisa by District Arch. Association in the District Museum Vidisa, in which this paper was read by me. Nagarch, B.L. pointed out in discussion that he has contributed a paper on "The Iconography of Bajara Matha at Gyarpur in the Journal of the Archaeological Congress and Seminar, 1972 published by the Department of Ancient Indian History, Culture and Archaeology. (The B.N. Chakravarty University, Kurukshetra).
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